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Joy Harjo's Crazy Brave: An Artistic Reclamation of Native American Women's Identity and Cultural Sovereignty

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Abstract: Native American women seem to struggle for emancipation from two kinds of status quo. One aspect focuses on breaking free from the colonial idea of the nation-state, while the other highlights resistance against heteropatriarchy that was planted into Native American tribes. This article applies theoretical lens of Andrea Smith on Joy Harjo's memoir *Crazy Brave* to highlight the involvement of settler colonialism in the obstruction of Native American consciousness. This paper investigates the resistive campaign of native women against intersectional politics of tribal men and colonial powers. Smith's idea of spiritual activism unfolds the difference of white feminism and colored feminism to uncover the systematic violence against native women. This paper also explores how Joy Harjo, through memory, metaphor, storytelling, and spiritual activism, critiques the dual oppression of settler colonialism and heteropatriarchy to reclaim indigenous identity and cultural sovereignty.

This research is an exploration of native women's adversity of keeping tribal nationalism over sexism as their survival strategy in an imperial nation state by using Joy Harjo's memoir *Crazy Brave* as a specimen.

Keywords: Native American women, settler colonialism, heteropatriarchy, identity, cultural sovereignty, spiritual activism

Introduction:

Joy Harjo's *Crazy Brave* preserves cultural and feminine agency by intertwining personal and tribal struggles. Harjo integrates tribal storytelling tradition to withstand colonial and patriarchal structures, highlighting the dual oppression faced by Native women; racism and heteropatriarchy. Kirsten Holst Peterson and Anna Rutherford's concept of "double colonization" aptly captures this intersection of struggles. Harjo employs the technique of using master's language against master in two ways; she exposes patriarchal violence on native women and at the same time dismantles the settler colonialism project. She uses song and music for her remembrance of past and memory. Her mother is a metaphorical representation of suffering and fading spiritual aura of indigenous women as she sings a song to forget about her sufferings and to reclaim her cultural heritage.

In every phase of her growth, Joy Harjo recalls her brave ancestors and compares them with her tribal men. She also undertakes the role of serving her tribe by being a poet and story teller as she says, "I was entrusted with carrying voices, songs, and stories to grow and release into the world" (2012, p.13). Women characters in *Crazy Brave* symbolize the quest for self-determination and cultural sovereignty that is still ongoing. In this respect, storytelling for Harjo is not only an act of preserving her tribe's cultural sovereignty but also a means to contest the colonial and patriarchal narratives. Andrea Smith's concept of "heteropatriarchy" contextualizes patriarchy as a colonial strategy to undermine egalitarian tribal structures. Drunken fathers and husbands in memoir are the representatives of colonial manipulation of tribal sovereignty. The memoir emphasizes native women's central role as cultural bearers and resisters, symbolizing the ongoing quest for sovereignty and self-determination.

The cyclical storyline of this memoir is internalized in its author from the indigenous memory and past. While situating herself within the scope of history, Harjo manages to combine personal experiences with collective tribal struggles. Through lyrical prose, Harjo honors Native women's resilience in sustaining their communities while exposing the violence inflicted by tribal men and colonial systems alike. Harjo uses fine imagery and cultural symbols as water, fire and four directions in her memoir. Using the sacredness of four directions in Native American culture as a narrative framework, the memoir reflects indigenous perspectives on life and identity. Dividing her life into four symbolic directions; east for beginnings, north for perseverance, south for passion, and west for

endings, Harjo portrays an indigenous worldview where memory and renewal coexist cyclically. This holistic structure underscores the intersectional alignment of Native feminism with cultural sovereignty. This paper analyzes how Harjo's use of storytelling and music reclaims cultural autonomy along with challenging the settler colonialism and patriarchal violence. By situating her personal journey within broader tribal struggles, I intend to analyze in what ways *Crazy Brave* becomes both a testament to indigenous survival and a critique of imperialist and patriarchal systems.

Literature Review

Joy Harjo's *Crazy Brave* holds up Smith's analysis concerning the gendered processes of settler colonialism by testifying domestic violence, cultural dispossession, and endurance in her memoir. During her *Poetry Foundation* interview (2012), Harjo narrates, "Writing *Crazy Brave* was my effort to face the history and assert my individual and collective story again as an Indigenous woman." This self-reflection indicates why narrative as resistance is powerful. Justice (2018) suggests the *Crazy Brave* as the text of cultural survivance and resilience. As Justice points out; "Harjo's memoir is the survivance of Native peoples in complete opposition to the kinds of erasures that settler colonial histories perform" (p. 64).

Navarro (2019) advocates that Harjo's narrative connects her personal journey to 'wider referent', linking her individual story to the collective indigenous community. This wound allows her to develop cohesive attitudes towards herself as a woman and as a writer, as well as towards the rest of the community (p. 51). Harjo's narrative reveals the impact of traumas on her identity formation as a woman and a writer, illustrating how writing functions as an open wound. As Butler (2006) highlights in *Gender Trouble*, this allows her to "develop cohesive attitudes towards herself... as well as towards the rest of the community" (pp. 51-52).

Lisa Kuhn (2022) also admires Harjo's practice of storytelling: "Stories are what remain after the final transcendence—death takes place. They are rebirth" (p. 87). Moreover, Mancelos (2006) in *Transfix me with love: Joy Harjo's discourse of memory and reconciliation* comments on Harjo's narration, "Harjo's poetry and poetic prose are haunted by those who are corroded by fear and revulsion: drunken tramps, suicidal women, annihilated old men – victims not only of colonialism but also of self-pity" (p. 54).

Color feminist scholars such as Andrea Smith, bell hooks and Audre Lorde also inform an understanding of Harjo's work even further. Andrea Smith's seminal work, *Conquest: Sexual Violence and American Indian Genocide* (2005) provides an access how settler colonialism targets Native women uniquely. Smith elaborates that "What is being depicted here is not simply sexual violence, but sexual violence as colonialism: the 'Indigenous people' are being invaded, occupied, and actively

raped" (p. 12) This lens is crucial in making sense of indigenous women's interactions with settler colonial institutions and the legacies that are at work to this day.

Smith (2005) on the same regards criticizes mainstream feminism for failing to capture complexity of oppression of Native women arguing that "mainstream feminist narratives often leave out the plight of Indigenous women under colonialism" (p. 137). In this regard, hooks (1989) argues that race and histories are equally important when coming up with the model to eradicate oppression, as she notes; "thus, oppression cannot be partitioned; a race issue, gender, and history are elemental" (p.15). These intersectional notions enhance Smith's wherein understanding of native women' live and explicate hooks' improved picture of Smith.

In addition, Harjo also assertively includes native spirituality as a way to take back power of their traditions and heritage. Ortiz (2015) commented, "Harjo uses poetry as her own 'transformative act against colonial silencing' to show the significance of commitment to cultural and linguistic survivance" (p. 87). Ortiz also agrees with the argument that Harjo's lyrical storytelling as the foundation of an effective colonial silence. Harjo uses traditional way of narrating her own history through storytelling. Audre Lorde (1984) inquires this argument by saying, "personal stories are political" (p. 36). Therefore, this discussion will provide a foundation to understand the stereotypical colonial narratives.

The above mentioned scholastic contributions have counterbalanced the titling pressure of all intersectional ideals regarding colonialism and cultural preservation. Somehow, these scholarships have neglected the colonial degradation of domestic and tribal life experienced by native women that is primarily discussed in *Crazy Brave*. This research paper examines the colonial implantation of heteropatriarchy in Native American tribes to unsettle native society. This paper amplifies the voices of Native women who struggle to reclaim their sovereignty by narrating their experiences of violence in a colonial world.

Theoretical framework

Andrea Smith's feminist critique of settler colonialism and heteropatriarchy is a powerful lens to analyze the systemic forces that have disrupted Native women, their sovereignty and tribal lives. In *Conquest: Sexual Violence and American Indian Genocide* (2005), Smith argues that settler colonialism functions through the control and subjugation of indigenous women so as to destabilize their communities. Harjo's remarks about native women struggles corroborate Smith's assertion, "colonialism does not target simply Native peoples collectively, but rather aims at dismantling indigenous women's central roles in community life" (p. 25).

Cultural erasure as another settler colonial tool dictates Native women's capacity to uphold familial and tribal connections. Smith, in the chapter titled 'Heteropatriarchy and the Three Pillars of

White Supremacy' of *Color of Violence: The INCITE! Anthology* (2006), asserts that the colonial apparatuses of boarding schools and Christian missions were all designed to distance indigenous children from their mothers and other extended family members. This alienation laid an immediate blow on matrilineal knowledge transmission. Matrilineal, instead of matriarchal, is used in this paper for two significant reasons: firstly, matrilineal suggests a horizontal relationship between genders in which women act as the pivotal unit of social structure without oppressing their male counterparts; and secondly it refers to a rejection of white patriarchal structures that keep women on the margins of society. In *Crazy Brave*, Harjo's depiction of the disconnection in her family reflects such systemic disruption. Smith captures that "boarding schools erase not only culture but the relational systems and structures that sustain it" (pp. 66-73).

Heteropatriarchy implanted hegemonic masculinity in native tribes that destabilized traditional egalitarian family structures. Smith, in *Native Americans and the Christian Right* (2008), heeds upon the pre-colonial indigenous egalitarian or matrilineal systems which were systematically replaced by patriarchal models. These heteropatriarchal models marginalize women and erode their leadership roles within families and tribes. Harjo's *Crazy Brave* illustrates the personal consequences of this systemic shift, particularly through her experiences of domestic violence. Smith's observation that "gender violence against Native women is not incidental but structural" highlights how heteropatriarchy weaponized familial relationships to perpetuate colonial domination (p. 25).

The regulation of indigenous womens' bodies as a site of colonial control further reveals the gendered dimensions of settler violence. Smith (2005), in *Conquest*, argues that "colonial control of Indigenous womens' bodies symbolized domination over the land itself," a strategy designed to disempower entire communities. However, Smith also points out that the female body is a site of resistance, where women can reclaim agency through cultural and spiritual practices. Harjo's feminist reclamation of her body and identity, embodies Smith's argument that "resistance begins with reasserting the sacredness of Native women's bodies and their roles in familial and tribal life (p. 25)"

While Storytelling serves as an aversive tool for indigenous feminist project to restore the lost indigenous tribal values, Smith (2005) asserts that "testimony is a political act that challenges colonial narratives by centering Indigenous women's voices" (p. 29). Harjo's memoir functions as such testimony, documenting her personal struggles alongside the broader systemic violence that disrupted her family. Harjo's resistance to these imposed norms through art and spirituality exemplifies the feminist assertion that reclaiming traditional roles is a critical act of decolonization and family restoration.

Smith highlights how settler colonialism and heteropatriarchy target Native women's familial and tribal lives, disrupting relational systems and imposing patriarchal norms. This framework provides a poignant narrative of these impacts while also illustrating the transformative power of indigenous women to reclaim their agency. Native women restore their self and tribal identity by

reclaiming cultural practices, rejecting imposed gender roles, and bearing testimony that resists colonial narratives of growth and development of Native life under colonial rule. This paper employs Smith's above discussed ideas to examine the challenges that native american women face for reclaiming their tribal sovereignty.

Analysis

Joy Harjo's *Crazy Brave* (2012) is a distinguished illustration of the miscellaneous challenges that native women face and become reconciled to socio-economic ills such as poverty, domestic violence and colonialism. Harjo's private experience in *Crazy Brave* serves as an exemplification of broader historical and colonial initiatives that affect indigenous egalitarian society. This memoir is an artistic illustration of the story of an empowered native woman and her fight against settler colonialism and patriarchy.

The natural world, including animals, water, and the sky, in *Crazy Brave* becomes an extension of Harjo's symbolic framework. She emphasizes that all beings are interdependent and are in horizontal relationship. She often refers to animals as messengers and guides such as her reference to hawk's flight as a reminder of freedom. She grounds her story in an Indigenous worldview that makes the environment and nature sacred. This resonates with Smith's observation in *Native Americans and the Christian Right* (2008) that, "colonial ideologies dehumanized both Native peoples and the natural world, separating them from their interconnectedness". Harjo uses her tribal symbolism as a tool to fight against colonial concept of verticality of nature.

The four directions that are North, South, East, and West as a recurring metaphor in *Crazy Brave* indicate balance, guidance and spiritual grounding. Harjo equates each direction with each stage of life, and uses it as a way of knowing and a connection to the Earth. This alignment with directions follows the holistic worldview within the many indigenous traditions as it emphasizes the harmony among all dimensions: physical, emotional, spiritual, and intellectual realms. Andrea Smith, in her chapter 'Heteropatriarchy and the Three Pillars of White Supremacy' from *Color of Violence: The INCITE! Anthology* (2006), writes about how colonial systems have strategically attempted to remove indigenous people from such structures because "such cosmologies provide a foundation for community strength". Such invocation by Harjo into the directions serves as resistance to erasure as they work in the lines as tools for reconnection with the cultural identity and to center oneself in the disrupted family structure. "We are born into these directions," Harjo writes, "each one pulling at us in turn," and thus illustrates how the directions offer not only guidance but also a reminder of interconnectedness in her journey of survival and resistance.

Fire is another such powerful symbol used in *Crazy Brave* and epitomizes transformation, destruction, and renewal. Using fire as a real event and a metaphor, Harjo relates it to her own

personal traumas and spiritual rebirth. Through this image of fire, she recalls difficult and losing times, yet she uses the regenerative aspects of it as a symbol of strength. Smith's critique of colonial violence underscores the ways in which the bodies and spirits of Indigenous women are targeted as part of a larger effort to destabilize their communities. "Colonial control of Native women's bodies symbolizes control over the land itself," Smith writes in *Conquest* (2006). For Harjo, fire becomes a counterforce to this control, a symbol of resilience and renewal even in the face of profound loss. In her words, "Fire came to me in dreams, not to destroy but to remind me of what cannot be extinguished"; so, the power of Indigenous identity and memory endures.

Andrea Smith's concepts of settler colonialism and heteropatriarchy serve as a foundation to dictate Harjo's struggles as a Native American woman. Harjo's recollection depicts the unuttered stories of Indigenous women facing colonial brutality and racial conflicts. She claims, "We had no steady ground beneath us. The land, the sky, the rivers—they belonged to the stories of our people, yet they were stripped from us piece by piece" (Harjo, 2012, p. 16). In this regard, Smith proclaims that "settler colonialism inherently relies on the subjugation of Indigenous women to justify land theft and the destruction of Indigenous communities" (p. 23). This denial serves as a way to dissociate Native women's tribal identity and cultural ties. Colonial powers strive to rupture the traditional ties of Indigenous people with their ancestral land. These factors make the Native American women liable to double oppression. Smith further discusses in *Conquest: Sexual Violence and American Indian Genocide* (2005) that "colonialism's goal is not only to occupy land but also to erase Indigenous bodies and identities, often through gendered violence" (p. 30). Harjo's memoir revives her physical agony and psychological trauma through articulation of a lost Native American history that was suppressed by the colonial narrative of conquest.

The abuse that Harjo endures in her familial context mirrors the broader societal violence perpetrated against Indigenous women by colonial structures. Harjo narrates, "My stepfather held us in a grip of terror. He believed women and children were inherently incapable of reason and it was his duty to break us into submission" (p. 41). The mistreatment from her stepfather illustrates the convergence of domestic violence. Patriarchal authority functions as an instrument of both family control and colonial oppression. This representation of double oppression corresponds with Smith's criticism of heteropatriarchy of what she describes as abuse of Indigenous women as a part of the structure of settler colonialism. Smith (2005) asserts about this foul play, "Heteropatriarchy is the logic that naturalizes social hierarchies by positing white, male, heterosexual supremacy as the norm" (p. 46). Sarah Deer (2015) contributes to this argument by stressing that "sexual violence against Native women is not an epidemic, but rather a direct consequence of colonialism" (p. 4). Deer's analysis, correspondingly, resonates in Harjo's story as the story points out the structural causes of the harm inflicted on Indigenous women.

Another major thematic presence in *Crazy Brave* is alcoholism, signifying how self-destructive behaviors among indigenous people stem from inter-generational trauma. Harjo also sets forth the colonial policy of planting alcoholism into native Americans to destroy their cultural and tribal values. Harjo presents that, "Alcohol was a spirit that haunted our homes, stealing away our fathers, brothers, and sometimes mothers. It was a weapon we turned against ourselves" (p. 73). This poignant observation testifies the colonial trauma - through which Native Americans suffered generation after generation- rather than flaws that colonial discourses claim to be inherent within Native communities. Even conventional Native American feminist framework, as Smith argues, fails to contextualize itself into such unique historical and cultural contexts and thus ignores these systemic strands of Indigenous women's oppression. Lee Maracle (1996) expresses in this regard by stating that "Indigenous women's oppression cannot be separated from the colonization of our lands and our bodies" (p. 75). Maracle's understanding affirms the way Harjo marks both addiction and violence as manifestations of a general colonial disempowerment.

Traditional Native writers are often more concerned with Institutional settler colonialism that imposes external pressures on native communities, but Harjo, along with criticizing colonialism and its structures, also foregrounds the ills of Native patriarchal structures in her own tribal community that also constrain women's autonomy. She notes, "The men in my family carried the weight of colonization, and in their effort to reclaim power, they sometimes forgot the power of the women who held them together" (p. 53). This quote illustrates tensions on Indigenous landmasses that arise when groups seek colonized identities as a strategy to resist colonized domination, but ultimately reinforce patriarchal structures that keep native women in a situation of victimhood. Harjo's narrative rejects these dynamics by claiming the crucial roles that indigenous women hold in sustaining cultural and spiritual continuity. This is where we recall bell hooks' critique of patriarchy which aligns female oppression with another universal system of domination. Hooks (2004) writes, "Patriarchy has no gender. It relies on both men and women to perpetuate its norms" (p. 21). Harjo's work demonstrates this dynamic in the context of Indigenous resistance.

In the midst of these conflicts, Harjo's recreation of voice and identity is an artistic act of resistance. She exercises her agency to resist the colonial machinery of silence that kept Indian voice suppressed. She writes, "To be a poet is to be a truth-teller, to insist on the dignity of every life" (p. 105). Her creativity serves as a strategy for survival and freedom to overcome the constraints imposed by internal and external forces. Renya Ramirez (2007) emphasizes the importance of such actions for cultural production by saying that, "Indigenous women use art and storytelling as a means of survival, creating a space where their voices can thrive despite systematic silencing" (p. 89). This outlook cultivates the political and developmental insight of Harjo's creative inclusions that resist the systematic exclusions of Native Americans from discourses of colonial history.

Spiritual resilience is deeply connected to Harjo's survival strategy. It shows that indigenous women draw strength from their cultural roots to resist the mechanisms of settler colonialism that rid Native Americans off their agency, land, and tribalism. Harjo's resistance against colonial and patriarchal oppression through her tribal-cum-spiritual resources connects her with her Muskogee heritage. She revived stories, songs, and rituals that the colonial system tried to erase. She writes, "The stories are our bones. They remind us of who we are, even when the world tries to make us forget" (p. 128). Harjo's journey aligns with Smith's observation that Native women's resistance is directly connected to communal survival because it subverts the colonial epistemology that dismantles Native ontology of Indian us. Likewise, Paul Gunn Allen (1996) also points out the aspects of spiritual change when she expresses that "For Indigenous women, spirituality is not separate from resistance; it is the foundation of their survival" (p. 61). Allen supports the concept discussed therein about spirituality as a tool for empowering the people and as a way of resisting the process of cultural eradication and tribal annihilation.

Harjo's portrayal of intergenerational trauma foregrounds the memoir's inquiry about native women's suffering even further. She draws allusions from history to showcase her existential concerns about the colonial heritage that has brought sorrows to her ancestors as she comments, "The pain of my grandmothers and grandfathers seeped into my bones, shaping who I am and the battles I must fight" (p. 90). This recognition of intergenerational trauma can be linked to Cathy Caruth's analysis of trauma as a concept unlike other wounds, which shape collective politics of memory and cultural identity. Caruth (1996) argues that "trauma is never fully assimilated as it occurs; rather, it haunts the individual and the community, demanding recognition and reckoning" (p. 4). Harjo's story shows this lingering effect, as she tries to end patterns of suffering while honoring her ancestors' strength.

In *Crazy Brave*, Joy Harjo depicts intersecting forces of settler colonialism, tribal patriarchy, poverty, and systemic violence. Harjo's experiences against the wider forces of colonial and patriarchal oppression emphasizes the necessity of regarding Native women's struggles as intensely personal, yet also as deeply political. She unveils the subject of the onslaught of such forces over Indigenous women's sovereignty. Harjo acknowledges that Indigenous women are concerned with tribal sovereignty as well as gendered discrimination and fight this twofold oppression to not only emancipate their tribes from colonial bondage but also liberate Indian women from patriarchal structures. Harjo identifies the possibilities of reclamation of Indigenous women's agency and sovereignty by employing art and storytelling as a medium of resistance against both colonial and patriarchal mechanisms. Her belief in liberating potentials of art and storytelling makes the reader realize that what cannot be expressed in political discourses because of institutional constraints can be said meaningfully and effectively through imagined alternatives that we call literature.

Conclusion

This paper situates Harjo's narrative as a seminal text in articulating the resilience of Native women. This research analyses the positionality of Native women as subjects of compounded colonial and patriarchal subjugation. Thus, native women face complex adversity by being cultural custodians and marginalized subject at the same time. The article navigates intersecting oppressions that native women face while striving to uphold cultural sovereignty. This research also frames Harjo's experiences of being an indigenous woman within the broader discourse of intersectional politics of settler colonialism and heteropatriarchy. This paper examines the role of tribal values and history for reclamation of indigenous woman's selfhood. The future researcher can extend the argument of this paper to read postcolonial texts for analyzing the manifestation of subaltern's agency. Moreover, this paper can also be used to extend the double oppression faced by Native women to read her suppression on the triple levels of class along with race and gender. This paper was based upon the idea that art and storytelling can be a medium of reclamation of a lost history for resisting hegemonic power as Harjo (2012) expresses, "To heal is to remember. And to remember is to honor what is sacred in life (p.134)".

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